

A Comparative Study of the Effect of Teaching Vocabulary Based on Corpus versus Association Technique on Iranian Postgraduates' Vocabulary Retention

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Abstract. This study was conducted to compare the impact of two vocabulary learning techniques, namely corpus and association technique on vocabulary recall of Iranian Postgraduates. Two intact classes including 50 male and female Postgraduates, participating in TOFEL preparation course at English College in Kermanshah, Iran, were selected to be a part of a 504 course. They were randomly assigned to corpus group and association group. They were given a pretest including MCQ and Words Persian Equivalents test to make sure that they are not familiar with vocabularies in question. The corpus group and the association group were taught based corpus and association technique respectively. After the treatment they were given a post-test, then a delayed post-test. The results indicated that the corpus group outperformed both in the short and long term scores in MCQ, and association group performed better in Words Persian Equivalents test. The results can have pedagogical implication for teachers and syllabus designers.

Keywords: corpus, association, short and long term retention

1 Introduction

Larsen-Freeman (2000), mentioned that for many years learning vocabulary was secondary to grammar learning in language acquisition due to the assumption held by some researchers. Recently this view has changed dramatically, and more and more researchers (e.g. Coady & Huckin, 1997), started to see that lexical competence as central to gaining the ability of effective communication. In order to communicate successfully and appropriately a certain number of words must be made familiar. The purpose of the present study is to find out whether students' vocabulary knowledge could be enriched through teaching new words based on corpus as compared with the association technique, and whether one is more effective in students' remember the meaning of the words more easily.

1.1 Background

Toward the end of twentieth century, a renewal of systematic attention to vocabulary learning across a number of proficiency levels and contexts was seen (Brown, 2001). Ranging from very explicit focus such as Lewis's Lexical Approach (1993,1997) to more indirect approaches in which vocabulary is combined into communicative tasks, attention to lexical forms is now more crucial to the development of language curricula (Nation & Newton, 1997). As remarked by Wilkins (1972), teaching a foreign language (FL) is not only a matter of presenting grammar. Little can be conveyed if one does not know grammar, but nothing can be conveyed if one does not know any vocabulary. Different methods have been proposed to enhance learners' vocabulary retention. These methods include a range of activities from many vocabulary books to corpus and associating the words with a word from first language (L1). The renewal of the interest in vocabulary teaching in the last 20 years has been attributed to two factors: First, availability of computerized databases of words (language corpora), and development of word centered or lexical approach in vocabulary instruction (Jezo, 2013).

Sinclair (2004), states that a new revolution in language teaching has been made in corpus-based language teaching. Applications derived from corpus investigations are found in a number of areas, e.g. translation, grammar, vocabulary, material and syllabus design. Halliday (2004), stated that corpus is a new study that can be used as a useful tool in language teaching. Since a large collection of authentic materials and advanced soft wares have been provided, a corpus makes an easy and quick analysis of the greatest amounts of linguistic data possible, and the learners are provided with a new approach to learn a language independently. Therefore it would be effective to employ such kinds of strategies to facilitate understanding and memorizing language materials. Richards, Platt and Platt, as cited in Mohammadi (2012), asserted that one of the ways which can be used to expand vocabulary knowledge is word association technique. Being important, word association

technique is an efficient technique through which learners can achieve a wide range of vocabulary knowledge, it can also help language learners support the long-term retention of vocabulary.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Different ways of learning vocabularies are usually used by the students such as using flash cards, notebook, referring to bilingual and monolingual dictionaries to find the meaning, or giving some synonyms and antonyms to name (Nemati, 2010). The problem is that vocabulary teaching in Iranian Language institutes is not based on useful instructions and techniques. Furthermore, many courses focusing on vocabulary do not consider the students aim in learning vocabulary, i.e. Iranian students are learning words either to pass the final exams at schools and universities or to perform well on the university entrance exams. Having this in mind the teacher should determine if his students need to use the words productively or they need just to memorize the meanings to understand the reading passages. That's what the research on vocabulary has rarely tackled. As stated by Partridge (2006), a useful tool in teaching vocabulary is analysis of corpus data. It provides valuable information for both students and teachers about how language is used in real-life situations. It is a collection of authentic texts (written or spoken transcripts) that are stored in an electronic form. According to Cohen and Aphek (1980), there is another technique called association which is a mnemonic link to some element or elements that would help learners to recall the word, including a link to meaning, sound, sound and meaning together, structure, context, mental image, letter(s) in the word, proper names, signs and so forth.

1.3 Significance of the Study

Different ways of learning vocabularies are usually used by the students such as using flash cards, notebook, referring to bilingual and monolingual dictionaries to find the meaning, or giving some synonyms and antonyms to name (Nemati, 2010). The problem is that vocabulary teaching in Iranian Language institutes is not based on useful instructions and techniques. Furthermore, many courses focusing on vocabulary do not consider the students aim in learning vocabulary, i.e. Iranian students are learning words either to pass the final exams at schools and universities or to perform well on the university entrance exams. Having this in mind the teacher should determine if his students need to use the words productively or they need just to memorize the meanings to understand the reading passages. That's what the research on vocabulary has rarely tackled. As stated by Partridge (2006), a useful tool in teaching vocabulary is analysis of corpus data. It provides valuable information for both students and teachers about how language is used in real-life situations. It is a collection of authentic texts (written or spoken transcripts) that are stored in an electronic form. According to Cohen and Aphek (1980), there is another technique called association which is a mnemonic link to some element or elements that would help learners to recall the word, including a link to meaning, sound, sound and meaning together, structure, context, mental image, letter(s) in the word, proper names, signs and so forth.

1.4 Research Questions

In order to investigate the effect of teaching vocabulary based on corpus versus word association technique on Iranian postgraduates' vocabulary retention the researcher attempted to answer the following questions:

Does teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique lead to a better performance on vocabulary test in the short term?

Does teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique lead to a better retention of words Persian equivalents in the short term?

Does teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique lead to a better performance on vocabulary test in the long term?

Does teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique lead to a better retention of words Persian equivalents in the long term?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

Based on the research questions mentioned above, the following null hypotheses emerged:

H₀₁: Teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique doesn't lead to a better performance on vocabulary test in short term.

H₀₂: Teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique doesn't lead to a better retention of words Persian equivalents in short term.

H₀₃: Teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique doesn't lead to a better performance on vocabulary test in long term.

H₀₄: Teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with the association technique doesn't lead to a better retention of words Persian equivalents in long term.

2 Relevant Studies

The work to be reviewed in this section consists of a number of experimental studies which have all investigated the impact of corpus or teaching vocabulary in context on vocabulary learning of EFL learners as well as the effectiveness of teaching vocabulary through mnemonic techniques respectively.

Jezo (2013), in a qualitative study called "Using Language Corpus in Teaching FL Vocabulary" showed the nature of a corpus-based approach, in which the effectiveness of this approach was confirmed by high scores the students obtained in their vocabulary tests after receiving the treatment as compared to the scores obtained before it.

In a similar study Jalilifar, Mehrabi and Mousavinia (2014), investigated the effect of enriching the vocabulary instruction with the printouts of concordance lines on learning and retention of Iranian EFL students. The results indicated that enriching vocabulary instruction with concordance lines improves students' achievement and retention of EFL vocabulary.

In contrast Qian (1996), compared the learning of SL words in both lists and contexts. He employed 63 Chinese university learners of English for learning a set of 15 English words. The No-Context group produced significantly better scores on a recall test than the Context group did; As a result of his findings, he challenges the assumption that contextualized vocabulary learning always leads to superior retention.

However there are some studies done on mnemonic devices. For example, Raugh and Atkinson (1975), compared the keyword method with various control procedures for learning a Spanish vocabulary. In all cases, the keyword method proved to be highly effective compared to the control group.

In another study Roediger (1980), looked at the method of loci along with three other well-known mnemonic methods. Results of the study revealed that all four mnemonic groups recalled the word list better than the control group.

Atay and Ozbulgan (2007), investigated the effects of memory strategy instruction along with learning through context on the ESP vocabulary recall of Turkish EFL learners. The result showed that memory strategies or mnemonic strategies can improve vocabulary learning.

2.1 Design

The present study aimed at investigating the effect of teaching vocabulary based on corpus as compared with association technique on Iranian postgraduates' vocabulary retention. Based on this topic four research questions emerged. In order to answer the main research questions, the following procedure would be implemented.

This research was quantitative experimental in nature. It enjoyed also a pre-test and post-test design to measure the learners' vocabulary retention and performance on vocabulary tests. Participants underwent some training sessions in which they were exposed to a number of new words through corpus and association technique. Then they were given a recall test to see whether memory for target words would be facilitated by these two types of instructions.

2.2 Participants

50 male and female students applied to be a part of a 504 course at English College in Kermanshah. They were divided into two classes, one was taught based on corpus and the other one based on association technique. So these two intact groups were the participants of this study. These participants were all Iranian and native speakers of Persian. They were either postgraduates, participating in TOFEL preparation course at English College Institute. Their range of age was 23 to 40 years old.

2.3 Instrumentation

The following instruments were applied for the study:

1. Text Book (504): 21 units of 504 Absolutely Essential Words (Bromberg, Liebb & Traiger, 2012), were used in the two groups. The main reason for selecting this book was that these students were participating in TOFEL courses and they needed to enrich their vocabulary knowledge of 504.

2. Teacher-Made Vocabulary Test (MCQ and Words Persian Equivalents Test): The researcher designed a vocabulary test comprising 20 multiple-choice items and a words Persian equivalent test from 504 book including 20 English words from the words of the textbook which they were taught to the participants during the treatment. The words were randomly selected for the tests. These two tests were administered for the two groups by the researcher. Since the tests were achievement tests, the content validity was ensured by drawing a table of specification. At first it was supposed to discard known words for the experiment, but on account of low scores of participants in the pre-test, the few known words were not discarded.

3. The Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) (1990-2012): Users can log in COCA website and fill out the search form. They can see the frequency listings or charts on the right hand of the form, and they can then click on any of the entries from the frequency lists to see the keyword in the context. They can also click on any of the KWIC entries to see even more context (about one paragraph) in the lower right-hand frame. But in this study the printouts of the concordance lines were used.

4. Association Codes for the Target Words: For each word, the specific code or codes along its pronunciation, English meaning, and Persian equivalents were provided for the study. For example: **gallant** (adj) , means :brave; showing respect for women.

شجاع- دلیر- شجاعانه- دلیرانه- مودب (خصوصاً نسبت به زنان)
کد : ماشین گلنت را کسی سوار میشه که شجاع و دلیره و به خانها احترام میزاره.

2.4 Procedure

The experiment was conducted at 12 sessions (each session 24 words of 504 book). Each presentation took approximately 45 minutes. In fact it was 10 sessions of treatment and 2 sessions for immediate post-test and delayed post-test.

The main study carried out in three steps: Pre-test, treatment along with post-test 1 (the so called, immediate post- test), and post-test 2 (the so called delayed post-test). The allotted time for teaching in both experimental groups was the same. Bellow each step would be explained briefly. A pre-test was administered a week before commencing the main study to both experimental groups. Before the main study the tests were piloted among learners. In order to prepare a list of words unknown to the participants, this pre-test was administered in 2 stages to the two groups, first: The participants received 20 multiple-choice questions; then they received 20 English words test, and they were asked to write their equivalents in Persian.

In the corpus group, the corpus was introduced to the learners. At first the teacher demonstrated the application of corpus as an aid to vocabulary learning, and then they were divided into groups of 5 to practice the new approach.

story about the confession. (Waller-in-court; Ms-WALLER: I was shocked that somebody would go under **oath**... (Voiceover)... on stand and lie. 's not as bad as Bill Clinton. NEWT-GINGRICH: He knew he was lying under **oath**. I didn't do the same thing. CONAN-O'BRIEN: After hearing th , just like every other man in that lifestyle did, you take an **oath** that you will kill if you need to, for your family. JAY-SCHADLER-1-AB# (Voicec utilization of these drugs. And of course, doctors themselves to practice the Hippocratic **Oath** of not doing harm. MORGAN: Do you think there s it, Holly Hughes? HOLLY-HUGHES-DEFE: Well, Nancy, you know, the hippocratic **oath** says, First do no harm. So when these doctors are giving prices are up 91 percent from February 20th, 2009, the day he took **oath** in D.C. until to today. I mean, what's going right? Why DHARUN-RAVI-1TYLE# That I had to go up there in front of the judge, under **oath**, and say that I did this because I had this hate for gay peopl husband's murder? It is the question lawyers will ask when she is under **oath** in the trial of Hemy Neuman. ANDREA-SNEIDERMAN-# Andrea Sr and gentlemen of the jury... HANSEN: (Voiceover) Listen to the plant manager, under **oath**, explaining what workers did to filter out the specks KEN-ANDERSON: In my heart, I know there was no misconduct whatsoever. LARA-LOGAN-1voice: Under **oath**, Anderson has said there's no w 're telling now the truth -- ERICA-HILL: Right. ERIN-MORIARTY: -- when you're under **oath**. I mean I think there's a real problem credibility. ER that's the way it will be in this case. When we took our **oath** of office in 2009, we pledged not only to look out for our precious How many were unemployed when he put his hand on that Bible and took that **oath** after your guy destroyed the economy, after Bill Clinton bu How many were unemployed when he put his hand on that bible and took that **oath** after your guy destroyed the economy, after Bill Clinton bu of how he assumes his brother's power. The secretary who took down the **oath**, Johnson asked Robert Kennedy for the wording of the oath. Ke

Fig. 2. Sample concordance lines for the word (*oath*)

The 252 words were chosen from 504 book, they were taught in the first experimental group by the help of corpus-based activities. The instructor made use of concordance lines taken from the COCA to teach words in the concordance lines. Participants were supposed to work collaboratively and read the sentences to guess the meaning of the words. The researcher was present to answer their questions and give them guidance.

In the association group, the association technique was explained in the first session of the experiment. A total of the same 252 words in corpus group, along their pronunciations, their English synonyms, their Persian equivalents and the allocated code or codes for them in Persian were presented to the association group. Consider for example, when an Iranian student is trying to learn the English word *abandon* the first word in 504 book, means *leave* and *give up*. In Persian we have a word *Abadan* (a city in Iran) which its pronunciation is

fairly similar to *abandon* in English. The association for this English word is [Mæn Abadan ra tærk mikonæm], it means [I'll leave Abadan]. So *abandon* means [tærk kærðan] in Persian.

After the procedure, the same test in pre-test was used as a post-test to both groups. To measure the short-term improvement of the students in the two experimental groups, immediately after finishing the teaching phase, the first post-test was administered. The learners took this recall test, to test their ability to retrieve the words or to measure their short-term retention. Two weeks after the immediate post-test, the same test, which now is called delayed post-test, was administered again. This is referred to as long-term retention. This test was given to them to measure their vocabulary knowledge and determine the effects of two types of instructions on long-term retention of vocabularies.

The tests were checked according to the following criteria. The testes included 20 multiple choice questions, and 20 English words which participants were supposed to choose one item and write their equivalents in Persian respectively. One point was awarded to any item that was correctly answered by the learners. As such the maximum possible score was 20 for each test and the total number of the tests was 40.

3. Data Analysis

After the collection of data, the participants' scores were obtained by adding up the correct answers. Relevant to the purpose and the nature of the obtained data after collection of data, the statistical measure that was used in this study was independent sample t-test since there were two groups of participants, and the effect of two types of instructions was compared.

3.1 Pre-Test Results Analysis

The first test that was given to the participants was pre-test which included one MCQ test and a words Persian equivalents test which were the same for both experimental groups. The results obtained from the pre-test in MCQ showed that the participants did not perform very differently regarding their knowledge of vocabulary (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean scores of the two groups' pre-tests in the MCQ

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	2.6200	.89303	.604	48	.549
association group	25	2.4400	1.19304			

Based on the data analysis it was observed that the mean of the participants' scores in the MCQ pre-test in the corpus group was 2.62, and the mean of the participants' scores in the same test in the association group was 2.44. ($t(25) = .604$; $P \text{ value} = .549$; $P > 0.05$).

The results obtained from the pre-test in the Words Persian equivalents, demonstrated that the participants' scores were not different regarding their knowledge of vocabulary, and it indicated that there was no significant difference between the performances of the two groups. Table 2 reveals the results of the independent sample t-test for the words Persian equivalents in the pre-test.

Table 2. Mean scores of the two groups' pre-tests in the Words Persian Equivalents

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	.8400	.88647	.264	48	.793
association group	25	.7800	.70828			

As shown in Table 2 both groups' performances on words Persian equivalents were fairly the same in the pretest, and participants in the two groups did not show a considerable difference.

3.2 Addressing the First Research Hypothesis

According to the first research question of the study, the researcher started to formulate a prediction by a null hypothesis. To test the hypothesis and to acquire the results of the study an independent sample t-test was conducted to compare post-tests' scores of the two groups in MCQ. The acquired results from the independent sample t-test are illustrated below. As demonstrated in figure 2 participants' mean score in corpus group was higher than participant's mean score in association group.

Fig.2. Bar chart of post-test in MCQ

Table 3, shows the results of the t-test clearly.

Table 3. Mean scores of the two groups' post-tests in the MCQ

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	13.0400	3.10215	3.793	48	.000
association group	25	10.1200	2.27889			

According to this table it was observed that the mean of the participants' scores in the corpus group was 13.0400, while the mean of the participants' scores in the association group was 10.1200. According to the meaningful level of significance gained from the data analysis which was 0.000 and comparing it with alpha level which was 0.05, we could be 95 percent certain that there was a meaningful difference between the two post-tests. So the first null hypothesis was rejected. ($t(25) = 3.793$; $P \text{ value} = 0.000$; $P < 0.05$; $13.0400 > 10.1200$).

3.3 Addressing the Second Research Hypothesis

To answer the second research question and to find the effect of teaching vocabulary via corpus, an independent sample t-test was run. The results obtained from the post-test in words Persian equivalents showed that participants in the association group performed much better than the corpus group did (Figure 3).

Fig.3. Bar chart of post-test in words Persian equivalents

Table 4. shows the results of the post-test in both groups in words Persian equivalents test.

Table 4. Mean score of the two groups' post-tests in the *Words Persian Equivalents*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	9.3600	3.02600	- 7.554	48	.000
association group	25	14.8800	2.04776			

As can be seen from this table, in this post-test, both groups performed well but the association group performed much better in words Persian equivalents than the corpus group did. According to the meaningful level of significance gained from the data analysis which was 0.000 and comparing it with alpha level which was 0.05, in can be concluded that there was a meaningful difference between the two post-tests. So the third null hypothesis was rejected.

3.4 Addressing the Third Research Hypothesis

The results obtained from the delayed post-test indicated a little variation. As can be seen in Figure 4, using corpus to teach new words seemed to have effect on students' performance in MCQ in long-term. The mean score obtained from the MCQ delayed post-test was less than that in post-test and participants mean score reduced this time.

Fig.4. Bar chart of delayed post-test in MCQ

Table 5, clearly illustrates that the students in the corpus group gained more knowledge of the target vocabularies after the instructional treatment in long-term.

Table 5. Mean score of the two groups' delayed post-tests in the *MCQ*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	12.4800	3.09731	3.667	48	.001
association group	25	9.5600	2.50133			

As Table 5 presents, the result revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the delayed posttests and this difference was not likely due to the chance. The results of the independent sample t-test showed a significant difference between the performance of the group that received concordance instruction (M=12.4800; SD= 3.09731), and the group in which they received association treatment (M=9.5600; SD=2.50133). (t (25) = 3.667 ; P value = 0.001 ; P < 0.05 ; 12.4800 > 9.5600).

3.5 Addressing the Fourth Research Hypothesis

The results of the delayed post-test showed that participants performed well in words Persian equivalents in both groups but not better than the post-test.

Fig.5. Bar chart of delayed post-test in words Persian equivalents

The data analysis in delayed post-test is demonstrated in Table 6.

Table 6. Mean scores of the two groups in delayed post-tests in the Words Persian *Equivalents*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
corpus group	25	7.7200	2.77669	8.173	48	.000
association group	25	13.6400	2.32522			

Based on this table, the mean of the participants' scores in the corpus group was 7.7200, while the mean of the participants' scores in the association group was 13.6400. ($t(25) = -8.173$; $P \text{ value} = 0.000$; $P < 0.05$; $7.7200 < 13.6400$). The results represented in this test rejected the fourth hypothesis. The $P < 0.05$, indicated the effect of teaching vocabulary based on corpus and association. However by the passage of time, the instructions impact was not so strong.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

As the results of the study indicated, there was a significant difference among scores of participants in corpus and association groups. Thus, results rejected the null hypotheses of the study. In line with previous similar studies on corpus approach, like that of Jezo (2013), this study confirms the powerful impact of the language corpus on learners' vocabulary retention and test performance in short term and long term. The results indicate that enriching vocabulary instruction with concordance lines improves students' achievement and retention of EFL vocabulary. The findings are consistent with Binkai (2012), who argues that the corpus-driven approach is helpful in vocabulary learning and can contribute to autonomous learning at the same time. While different studies have been done in this area, all the investigations had not the same outcome. And there were some which had conflict with the results of this study, for instance, in a study conducted by Qian (1996), the learning of SL words in both lists and contexts was compared. The No-Context group produced significantly better scores on a recall test than the Context group did.

Based on the studies on association technique, the finding of this study is consistent with Siriganjanavong (2013), who investigated the effects of mnemonic keyword method on the vocabulary acquisition and retention. He concluded that words taught by MKM could be better recalled both in short-term and LTM. In line with previous similar studies Baleghizadeh and Ashoori (2010), Amiryousefi and Ketabi (2011), and Jenpattarakul (2012), this study confirms the effectiveness of the keyword method and mnemonic technique, on learners' memory in recalling and retention of words Persian equivalents.

Dissimilar results in the related studies demonstrate that in some experiments instruction of vocabulary based on corpus and association may have positive effect on learning vocabulary but in other trials there is not any impact on their learning.

Vocabulary, as already noted, is a crucial component of learning a SL. Language learners are faced with the task of how to store and retrieve words and how to improve vocabulary learning efficiency.

This study aimed to introduce the techniques called corpus-driven learning and association technique, to Iranian EFL learners, and explore the effectiveness of the methods on vocabulary retention of the students in short-term and long-term. The obtained outcome of this study illustrated that there was a significant difference between the scores of the students' pre-test and scores of their post-test as well as their delayed post-test scores.

The study showed that students in corpus group performed much better in vocabulary tests both in short-term and long-term with corpus condition, than with association, and students in association group performed better in recalling the words Persian equivalents in short-term and long-term, though its effectiveness reduced over time. According to these findings the two methods may turn out to be useful for EFL learners. As a result, this study confirms using these two techniques in enhancing learners' performance in retaining the words in memory.

4.1 Pedagogical Implications

There are some implications that seem to be relevant to the classroom. First, teachers need to know that less attention is paid to vocabulary than to other language skills. As most training programs rarely include vocabulary teaching methods in the curriculum, many classrooms rarely address the word learning need of students directly. Teachers spend most of their time on grammar and they assume that the students will build their own vocabulary items in other activities. The teachers and the students must bear in mind that vocabulary learning does not occur unless the learners are able to transfer their vocabulary knowledge to a context, other than the one in which they learned the words.

Students engaging in corpus-driven learning environment must first familiarize themselves with the use of the computer and the concordancing program. So, the teacher should provide an initial tutorial for the students. The provided examples taken from COCA showed the nature of a corpus-based approach, in which the concordances seen on the printed version allow students to examine the vocabulary in their natural context. The corpus' massive collection of texts has given us access to a lot of information regarding spoken and written English that was previously unavailable.

Now it is clear that the corpus language researchers, syllabus designers and instructors could have access to a lot of information via corpus for both spoken and written English. That way they would be able to help EFL learners' to improve their vocabulary knowledge as well as speaking and writing more effectively. From this it is highly advocated for syllabus designers and teachers to apply computer corpus-data as a source for EFL vocabulary selection and instruction in particular and why not EFL teaching and learning in general.

Some pedagogical implications can also be drawn from the study for using association technique. First using this technique should be one of the alternatives for teaching hard to remember or low frequency words.

As the findings of the study showed that the method could enhance learners' performance in retaining the words in memory. To prevent the new information from fading, teachers might use different types of mnemonic technique along with other methods such as asking learners to repeat new words, do vocabulary exercises, or create a sentence with new vocabulary to enable the learners to transfer the information into the long-term memory. Furthermore, this technique becomes a tool for storing and retrieving, and expanding vocabulary size. It helps students to retain the words in long-term memory and it can be very effective and can make the students motivated and the classroom more interesting. Motivation is considered to be the main factor that affects the storing, retaining and recalling of the information being learned.

4.2 Suggestions for Further Studies

This is an empirical study which calls for improvement and further study in implementing such models of vocabulary teaching. While the study findings depicted significant effects of teaching vocabulary through corpus and also association on improving the vocabulary knowledge of the language learners, it would be beneficial to do more studies on these issues in order to generalize the findings of the study. It is required to conduct studies with larger sample size to make better generalization and confirmation of the results of this investigation. It would be beneficial to replicate this study on using corpus in FL classes from intermediate to advanced level.

The present study suggests that future research should be conducted in ESP (English for Special Purposes) areas. It may examine the effects of ESP vocabulary instruction through the corpus-driven learning on students' vocabulary learning. In ESP training courses, besides language knowledge, vocabulary is the main focus.

Since it appears that investigation related to the effects of using mnemonic associations has attracted the attention of few researchers in Iran, to provide more evidence for the effectiveness of such methods in natural setting, further comprehensive research in this area is recommended. Further research is also suggested on the effects of some factors such as the learner's beliefs and motivation about language learning on using associations and student's performance.

In addition, it would be interesting to replicate this study with other graders who learn English as a FL, which may shed light to interesting results, ideas and directions in the field.

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